

The Effect of Leadership and Management Innovation on Company Performance in Sankita Hotels with Organizational trust as a Mediation Variables

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Abstract: *This study aims to analyze the influence of leadership and management innovation on company performance at Sankita Hotels with organizational trust as a mediating variable. The research sample consisted of 50 respondents. The sampling technique used was accidental sampling, which is part of a non-probability sampling technique. Data analysis used path analysis. The results showed that: (1) ideal indicators of influence, motivational inspiration, and intellectual stimulation contributed to leadership variables; Indicators of line expansion, new products, and completely new products contribute to the management innovation variable; Benevolence, reliability, competence, honestly and openness indicators contribute to organizational trust variables; Indicators of financial perspective, customer perspective, internal business process perspective, and learning and growth perspective contribute to company performance variables. (2) Leadership and management innovation can influence organizational trust. (3) Leadership and management innovation can affect company performance. (4) Organizational trust can affect company performance. (5) Leadership and management innovation can affect company performance through organizational trust.*

Keywords: *Leadership, Management Innovation, Organizational Trust and Company Performance*

I. Introduction

The development of the world of tourism has experienced changes so fast and extraordinary. This is following what was conveyed by Naisbitt who said that the tourism industry business will become the largest industry in the world (Naisbitt, 1994: 131). Hotels are a tourism component that has an important role in the development of tourism in an area, in this case in Tegal Regency, Central Java Province. In building a hotel in an area, a large investment is needed and the existence of a hotel can also improve the welfare of the surrounding community with a large number of workers absorbed and can grow other business sectors where its existence can support the hotel business.

In organizations or companies, the world of tourism, in this case, the hotel industry, each of these businesses certainly has short-term and long-term goals to be achieved through the activities carried out. To achieve the planned goals, it is necessary to plan and manage human resources optimally. The term human resources refer to individuals in organizations who work together to achieve organizational goals (Schein in Mangkunegara, 2009: 23).

Human resources are the most important thing that an organization has, one of the implications is that the most important investment made by an organization is in the field of human resources (Handoko, 2004: 4). Therefore, for an organization to achieve maximum performance, it requires fair and satisfactory treatment of every human resource who works in the organization.

Every hotel organization is required to be able to compete to survive in the competition in the millennial era. The strategy to always be able to compete is by strengthening the organizational capacity and

resources they have (Sudarmanto, 2009: 1). However, the problem of human resources is a challenge in itself for management because the success of management depends on the quality of the resources that oversee it.

Many people believe that leadership is a way to improve their personal, social, and professional lives. Companies are looking for people with leadership abilities because they believe such people bring special assets to their organization and will ultimately increase the organization's profits. Also, leadership has received the attention of many researchers around the world. An analysis of leadership studies shows that there are a variety of different theoretical approaches to explaining the complexity of the leadership process.

Some researchers interpret the concept of leadership as a trait or behavior, while others view leadership from an information processing or relationship perspective. Taken together, research findings on leadership from all of these fields paint a picture of a much more sophisticated and complex process from an oversimplified view.

Management innovation has been defined in various perspectives according to the analysis used to suggest that a more macro approach tends to encourage more variation in the definition. Linking innovation in an organizational context that includes implementing ideas for restructuring or cost savings, improved communications, new technologies for production processes, new organizational structures, and new personnel programs or plans.

Management innovation corresponds to the deliberate introduction and application of a role, group, or organization of ideas, processes, products or procedures, new to the relevant adoption unit, designed to provide significant benefits to individuals, groups, organizations, and society. This implies that the context in which new ideas, products, services and activities are implemented will determine whether they can be considered an innovation in a specific context.

For companies, innovation is very important and is a continuous process with one another without stopping at one point. Innovation is also needed as a driver for companies to continue to grow and develop. So that companies that are always innovating are expected to improve company performance. Therefore, innovation must always exist and be built in the body of the company forever.

Company performance is an organization's ability to achieve its goals by using resources efficiently and effectively (Daft, 2000; Devie, 2013). Good company performance will have an impact on dividends that will be received by shareholders because dividends are always based on the current year's net income and net income is a measure of company performance (Christiawan and Tarigan, 2007: 3).

The development of hotel development in the Guci natural tourism area in the Tegal Regency is very fast so that it can create very high business competition so that every company must have the ability to innovate in its business management. Han (1998) in his research stated that when a company faces a business environment that has very high competition, then the company must have the ability to innovate to improve quality. Kasali (2010) states that innovation is the ability to see things in a new and sometimes out of the box way.

Organizational performance or organization performance is the goal of running a company. Therefore, the success of a company can be seen from its performance. Rue and Byard (1977: 221) define performance as an outcome that can be achieved by the organization. Performance measurement or benchmark is a measurement of the results of strategy implementation, if it is considered good, it will be used as a measure of performance in the future. Waterhouse and Svendsen (1998: 59) state that performance is an action that can be measured and is a reflection of the achievement of the quantity and quality of work produced by individuals, groups and organizations.

The development of science and technology today leads to global changes. This change has become a phenomenon that must be anticipated by various parties, both individually and in an organization. Anticipation is carried out in the context of adjusting to various demands and increasingly complex competition.

Advances in science and technology have also shown and impacted the development of organizational work activities, both those engaged in services and organizations engaged in manufacturing. In general, every organization has the same goals, namely short-term goals and long-term goals, where the short-term goal is to

get the maximum profit or profit that will later be used in achieving its long-term goals, namely ensuring the survival of the organization in the future.

Hotel Sankita is one of the hotels located at the foot of Mount Slamet. It is also required to improve employee performance. This is because competition from similar companies is getting tighter. To be able to maintain its existence in the fierce competition, Hotel Sankita strives to provide good service to users of the services offered for the survival of the hotel.

One of the services that have an important role in boosting revenue Hotel Sankita is one of the facilities intended for tourists who want classy services. Efforts made by management in human resource management aim to improve employee performance, thereby encouraging the improvement of the quality of services provided to tourists who visit and stay overnight.

The trust that the leader gives to his subordinates has a positive impact on his employees. Therefore, a leader who has a certain leadership style will be reflected in the leader. Subordinates will also see the leader figure based on how the leader behaves and reflects behavior that can lead to responses from subordinates. Subordinates will judge the leader to be trusted or not based on his leadership style.

Trust is a person's willingness to rely on other people in whom we have confidence. Trust is a mental condition based on a person's situation and social context. When a person makes a decision, he will prefer decisions based on the choices of people whom he can trust more than those who are less trusted.

II. Literature Review

Company Performance

Performance is a work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, following their respective authorities and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals (Saputra, 2013: 23). Company performance is a description of the achievement of the implementation of an activity or program/policy in realizing the goals, objectives, mission and vision of the company. Performance reporting is a reflection of the obligation to present and report the performance of all activities that need to be accounted for (Halim, 2013: 268).

Company performance is an organization's ability to achieve its goals by using resources efficiently and effectively (Daft, 2000; Devie, 2013). The company's performance can be said to be the result of the company's operational activities. Operational activities in the financial statements are shown by the achievement of net income. Profit is the difference between revenue and expenses so that managers in managing the company will try to maximize revenue and reduce expenses. The activity of maximizing revenue is also called an increase in profitability while reducing expenses is also called an increasing inefficiency. Good company performance will have an impact on dividends that will be received by shareholders because dividends are always based on the current year's net income and net income is a measure of company performance (Christiawan and Tarigan, 2007: 3).

Organizational Trust

The trust exists when a group believes in the trustworthiness and integrity of a partner. Trust is an expectation held by an individual that someone's speech is reliable. A trusted group needs to have high integrity and can be trusted, which is associated with quality, namely: consistent, competent, honest, fair, responsible, helpful and kind. Trust is the belief that service providers can use it as a tool to forge long-term relationships with customers to be served.

Trust is the desire of one party to get treatment from another party in the hope that the other party will take important actions to meet these expectations, regardless of its ability to monitor or control the other party. Trust is a product generated between the two actors in an exchange with more concern for the costs and benefits of certain behavior as stipulated in the contract. In other words, trust is a belief, a feeling, or an expectation of the other party which is the expertise, reliability and concern of the other party, or the perception of confidence in the exchange partner's reliability and integrity (Soegoto, 2014: 273).

Trust is an interpersonal relationship and a complex organizational concept. Trust occurs when parties have certain perceptions of being in favor of each other which allows the relationship to achieve the expected results. Someone believes, groups or institutions will be free from worries and the need to monitor the behavior of other parties, partially or completely. Trust is an efficient way to reduce transaction costs in social, economic and political relations (Nawawi, 2012: 21).

Maharsi and Fenny (2006: 36) explain that there are 3 types of trust, namely: (1) Trust in object attributes, this belief connects an attribute with an object, such as a person, goods or services. Where through object attributes, customers state what is known about something in terms of its attribute variation, (2) Trust benefit attributes, are customer perceptions of how far certain attributes generate and provide certain benefits, and (3) Trust the benefits of objects, represent customer perceptions about the extent to which certain products or services will provide certain benefits.

Lita (2009: 72) explains that two things affect trust, namely, (1) credibility, related to the company's ability to fulfill all of its obligations, a company that successfully fulfills all its obligations should generate a willingness to buy to continue its relationship, and (2)) Concern, related to the company's willingness to care about the fate of its customers.

Thus, it can be concluded that what is meant by a trust is a positive expectation that other people or companies can depend on, they will respect their commitments, they will treat us fairly, and they care. Trust in a relationship, especially in a business relationship, is very important. Trust is one of the main keys held by customers in making decisions.

Leadership

In order to achieve company goals, the role of a leader is needed. In addition, leaders in a company also have a role in smoothing the company's business. A leader in a company can be likened to the captain of a cruise ship, which is in charge of determining the direction, running the ship, and making decisions about where to take the cruise ship. Leadership is the ability to influence a group to achieve the goals of a vision or a series of goals (Colbert, Judge, Choi & Wang, 2012: 2).

According to Winardi (2008: 2), a leader is a person who because of his abilities with or without official appointment can influence the group he leads to exert joint efforts towards the achievement of certain goals. Leadership can be defined as a social influence process in which a leader invites his subordinates to participate in efforts to achieve organizational goals. At the individual level, for example, leadership here includes monitoring, guiding, inspiring and motivating (Kinicki and Kreitner, 2010). Leadership is defined as the ability to influence a group of people to achieve a vision or a set of goals (Robbins and Judge, 2009). Leadership is a process by which an individual can influence a group of individuals to achieve goals (Shani, 2009).

Based on the statements of several experts above, it can be concluded that leadership is a process of directing and giving influence to employees based on a leader's ability to direct his employees to achieve organizational goals that have been set in certain situations.

III. Management Innovation

Management is formed from the Latin "manus" and agree ". Manus means hand and agree to means to do. So that if it is combined into management, it means handling. The word manager is translated into English as to manage, with changes when it is positioned as a noun to management and manager. What is then absorbed into Indonesian into the word management or management, from here it is known that the notion of management is the art of doing work through people (Usman, 2006: 3). Furthermore, innovation is the center of business activities that want to launch new business units and renew their strategic business units (Floyd et.al. 2005). Innovation is also defined as the creation and implementation of new processes, products and services as well as delivery methods that can be seen as the result of significant improvements in terms of income, efficiency, effectiveness or quality in a market (Ulijn, 2004: 15). More completely, borrowing an understanding from the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) innovation is a change introduced

to improve the operation of a system, its performance, stakeholder satisfaction, at the same time. Therefore innovation has characteristics including, first, innovation is a product, process or procedure that can be touched in an organization or across organizations. Second, innovation must be something new that is introduced within a certain scope of the organization. Third, innovation is not a routine change. Fourth, innovation must generate measurable benefits. Fifth, innovation must have an impact on society (OECD Publishing, 2009). So it can be concluded that innovation is a change made to create better conditions with the characteristics of this change is something new, not a routine, has an effect, and generates a profit.

IV. Research Methods

Research Design

Based on the research objectives, this research is explanatory through hypothesis testing to test the nature of the relationship between variables (correlational and causal tests). This research is a survey research using structured interviews with an individual analysis unit of employees who work at Hotel Sankita as respondents.

Population and Sample

The population in this study were all employees who work at Hotel Sankita, amounting to 100 people, while the sample used in this study amounted to 50 respondents. The sampling method in this study was carried out by using accidental sampling technique which is part of the nonprobability sampling technique. This form of sampling is based on chance, that is, anyone who happens to meet this researcher and is deemed suitable as a data source will be the sample of this study (Sugiyono, 2010: 59). Respondents in this study were employees of Hotel Sankita. Based on the Slovin formulation, it is determined that the number of samples as objects of observation is 50 respondents. This number is considered representative or represents the population.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis technique in this study is to use the path analysis technique. Path analysis was first introduced by Sewall Wright in the 1930s. Path analysis is an extension of multiple linear regression analysis. Path analysis is a technique for analyzing causal relationships that occur in multiple linear regression if exogenous variables affect endogenous variables not only directly but also indirectly (Ghozali, 2005).

V. Research Results and Discussion

Path Analysis

The structural equation model used as a whole consists of two exogenous variables, one mediating variable and one endogenous variable. The figure below shows that the standard effect consists of estimating the direct effect, estimating the indirect effect and estimating the total effect. The results of the analysis show that all paths, both direct, indirect and total in the structural equation model have a significant effect because they are greater than the p-value > 0.05.

Table 1. Research Variable Causality Test and Hypothesis Test

No.	Hip	Variable			Regression Coefficient		
		Exogenous	Mediation	Endogenous	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total
1	H ₁	Leadership	Organizational Trust	-	0,664	-	-
	H ₂	Leadership	-	Company Performance	0,072	0,664 x 0,361 = 0,240	-
	H ₃	-	Organizational Trust	Company Performance	0,361	-	-
	H ₄	Leadership	Organizational Trust	Company Performance	-	-	0,072 + 0,240 = 0,312

2	H ₁	Management Innovation	Organizational Trust	-	0,253	-	-
	H ₂	Management Innovation	-	Company Performance	0,512	0,253 x 0,361 = 0,091	-
	H ₃	-	Organizational Trust	Company Performance	0,361	-	-
	H ₄	Management Innovation	Organizational Trust	Company Performance	-	-	0,512 + 0,091 = 0,603

Source: Data Processed, 2020

First Hypothesis

Figure 1. Substructure Equations 1

The first hypothesis states that leadership and management innovation has a positive and significant effect on organizational trust. Hypothesis test results show that the resulting path coefficient value for both paths is greater than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05). This means that empirically and theoretically, leadership and management innovation have a positive and significant effect on organizational trust.

Second Hypothesis

Figure 2. Substructure Equations 2

The second hypothesis states that leadership and management innovation has a positive and significant effect on company performance. Hypothesis test results show that the resulting path coefficient value for both paths is greater than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05). This means that empirically and theoretically, leadership and management innovation have a positive and significant effect on company performance.

Third Hypothesis

Figure 3. Substructure Equations 3

The third hypothesis states that organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on company performance. Hypothesis test results show that the resulting path coefficient value is greater than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05). This means that empirically and theoretically organizational trust has a positive and significant effect on company performance.

Fourth Hypothesis

Figure 4. Substructure Equations 4

The fourth hypothesis states that leadership and management innovation has a positive and significant effect on company performance through organizational trust. The effect of exogenous variables on the mediating variable and the effect of the mediating variable on endogenous variables can be seen through the standard coefficient values of direct, indirect and total influence. Hypothesis test results show that the resulting path coefficient value is greater than 0.05 (p-value > 0.05). This means that empirically and theoretically, leadership and management innovation have a positive and significant effect on company performance through organizational trust.

VI. Discussion

1. The Effect of Leadership and Management Innovation on Organizational Trust

Leadership is a process of social influence in which a leader invites his subordinates to participate in achieving organizational goals. At the individual level, for example, leadership here includes monitoring, guiding, inspiring and motivating. The findings of the research results for the leadership variable show a positive and significant effect on organizational trust. The most dominant indicator of leadership influencing organizational trust is idealized influenced and the most dominant indicator of management innovation influencing organizational trust is a new product (me too - product). This means that good leadership in Sankita Hotel management and innovation in management can significantly increase customer confidence in Sankita Hotel's image.

2. The Effect of Leadership and Management Innovation on Company Performance

Management innovation is a process consisting of planning, organizing, mobilizing and controlling actions, which are carried out to determine and achieve predetermined targets through the use of human and other resources. So it can be concluded that management is a process of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and controlling existing resources to achieve predetermined goals. The results of the research for management innovation variables show a positive and significant effect on company performance. The most dominant indicator of leadership influencing company performance is idealized influence and the most dominant indicator of management innovation affecting company performance is new products (me too - product). This means that the leadership and management innovation carried out by the Sankita Hotel management can significantly improve the performance of the Sankita Hotel.

3. The Effect of Organizational Trust on Company Performance

Trust is the belief that service providers can use it as a tool to forge long-term relationships with customers to be served. Trust is the willingness or belief of an exchange partner to establish a long-term relationship to produce positive work. The results of the research for organizational trust variables show a positive and significant effect on company performance. The indicator of the organizational trust that most dominantly affects company performance is openness. This means that the trust of customers in the reputation of Hotel Sankita will be able to maximize the performance of Hotel Sankita.

4. The Influence of Leadership and Management Innovation on Company Performance through Organizational Trust

The results of research on leadership and management innovation on company performance through the organizational trust are important in this discussion because it has been proven that leadership and management innovation can improve company performance through organizational trust. However, the results of the research conducted show that leadership can be through organizational trust in influencing company performance, while management innovation cannot be through organizational trust in influencing company performance. The company's performance indicator that is most dominantly influenced by leadership and management innovation through organizational trust is the internal business process perspective. This means that leadership and management innovation can affect the performance of Hotel Sankita through customer trust in the image of Hotel Sankita.

VII. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusion

Based on the results of research that has been carried out to test the hypothesis and answers to the proposed problem formulations, the researcher can draw the following conclusions:

1. Based on the results of descriptive analysis, it is found that:

- a. Leadership Variables. Ideal indicators of influence, inspirational motivation, and intellectual simulations contribute to the leadership variable. Idealized influence is the most dominant indicator in the leadership variable with an average value of 4.06.
- b. Management Innovation Variables. The indicators of line expansion, new products, and completely new products contribute to the management innovation variable. The new product (me too product) is the most dominant indicator in the management innovation variable with an average value of 4.05.
- c. Organizational Trust. Benevolence, reliability, competence, honestly and openness indicators contribute to organizational trust. Openness (openness) is the most dominant indicator in the organizational trust variable with an average value of 4.18.
- d. Company performance. Indicators of financial perspective, customer perspective, internal business process perspective, and learning and growth perspective contribute to company performance variables. The internal business process perspective is the most dominant indicator in the company's performance variable with an average value of 4.06.

2. Leadership and management innovation can influence organizational trust.
3. Leadership and management innovation can affect company performance.
4. Organizational trust can affect company performance.
5. Leadership and management innovation can affect company performance through organizational trust.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research and discussion, the author tries to provide suggestions that might be followed up as follows:

1. For Hotel Sankita, Guci, Tegal
 - a. Based on the research results, it is known that the leadership variable which is located in the sub-indicator "opportunity for leadership to come up with creative ideas" gets the lowest score (188), therefore the leadership of Hotel Sankita, Guci, Tegal, is advised to provide opportunities for all employees who have ideas. creative to express their opinions with the aim that the organization has a large selection of ideas that can be developed for the advancement of Hotel Sankita, Guci, Tegal.
 - b. Based on the results of the study, it is known that the management innovation variable which is located on the sub-indicator "promotional design carried out is very elegant and classy" gets the lowest score (191), therefore Hotel Sankita, Guci, Tegal, is advised not only to pay attention to the design and form of promotion. undertaken, but must also consider the promotional price offered to compete with other competitors in similar business fields.
 - c. Based on the results of the study, it is known that the organizational trust variable which is located in the sub-indicator "service provided" gets the lowest score (190), therefore Sankita Hotels, Guci, Tegal are advised to improve the quality of service for customers who have frequently stayed at hotels. Also, it is also necessary to improve facilities as a form of service provided by providing free wifi spots, free snacks and soft drinks and expanding entertainment spaces such as parks and swimming pools.
 - d. Based on the research results, it is known that the company performance variable which is located in the sub-indicator "the ability to interact with customers" gets the lowest score (190), therefore Hotel Sankita, Guci, Tegal, is suggested to improve the workability of employees through service training for employees, implementation Strict service SOP, and supervision of leaders in service activities in hotels.
2. For further researchers, this research can develop using other methods in researching leadership, management innovation, organizational trust and company performance, for example through in-depth interviews with respondents, so that the information obtained can be more varied than questionnaires whose answers are already available.

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